

Asparagus Racemosus-Mediated Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles with Promising Biomedical Properties

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Abstract:

In this study, the AgNPs were successfully synthesized using the aqueous root extract of *Asparagus racemosus*. The formation of AgNPs was confirmed by various characterization techniques, including UV-vis spectroscopy, which revealed the characteristic surface plasmon resonance peak around 380 nm. Phytochemical analysis of the AgNPs indicated the presence of various bioactive compounds derived from *Asparagus racemosus* root extract. These compounds, including flavonoids, saponins, terpenoids, steroids, and glucosides, contribute to the therapeutic potential of the AgNPs. The AgNPs displayed considerable therapeutic potential in various applications, including antimicrobial, antioxidant, and antimutagenic activities. The antimicrobial efficacy of the AgNPs was evaluated against pathogenic bacteria, and they demonstrated significant inhibitory effects on the growth of *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Bacillus subtilis*, indicating their potential as antimicrobial agents. Furthermore, the AgNPs exhibited strong antioxidant properties, effectively scavenging free radicals, making them potentially useful as natural antioxidants. The AgNPs demonstrated antimutagenic activity in the Ames test, indicating their ability to protect DNA from mutagenic damage and potentially reducing the risk of genetic mutations. Overall, the use of *Asparagus racemosus* root extract in the synthesis of AgNPs presents a promising approach, as the nanoparticles exhibited significant therapeutic potential in various biomedical applications. These findings open avenues for further research and development of AgNPs as effective and sustainable treatments for various health issues.

Keywords: *Asparagus racemosus*, antimicrobial activity, antioxidant activity, antimutagenic activity.

1. Introduction:

The environment has suffered significant harm due to urbanization and industrial growth. To tackle this issue, it is crucial to adopt sustainable approaches aligned with the principles of green chemistry. These approaches aim to develop cost-effective and eco-friendly methods for producing advanced materials (Chokshi et al., 2016; Pandian et al., 2015). The field of nanoscience, encompassing disciplines such as chemistry, biochemistry, biology, and chemical engineering, has shown significant interest in the unique physicochemical characteristics of nanoscale noble metals, such as silver and gold (MubarakaAli et al., 2011; Iravani et al., 2011; Yamal et al., 2013; Rangayasami et al., 2020; Amina et al., 2020). Nanoparticles (NPs) have gained worldwide recognition in the fields of material science and medical research. Silver (Ag) and gold (Au) are considered noble metals due to their exceptional biological and pharmacological properties (Wijnhoven et al., 2009; Amina et al., 2020). Specifically, metallic nanoparticles have proven beneficial in various areas such as dentistry, wound healing, pharmaceuticals, surgery, catalysis, and biomedical devices (Merga et al., 2007; Navaladian et al., 2007; Nickel, 2000).

In recent times, their inherent antibacterial properties have led to their application in various fields, including packaging, food processing, cosmetics, textiles, medical devices, and biosensors (AshaRani et al., 2009; Pollini et al., 2011; Patil et al., 2012; Bhattacharya et al., 2008; Amina et al., 2020). Studies have indicated that nanoparticle (NP)-based medications demonstrate enhanced effectiveness due to their distinctive optical and electrical properties (Khan et al., 2017; Unser et al., 2015). The Surface Plasmon Resonance mechanism, a widely recognized attribute of NPs, contributes to their heightened efficacy (Navaladian et al., 2007; Khan et al., 2017). The electrical and therapeutic properties of NPs depend on their morphology, size, and shape (Chun et al., 2010; Azeez et al., 2017; Balan et al., 2016). Conventional techniques for NP synthesis, including chemical, thermal, hydrothermal, and photosynthetic methods, often involve the use of hazardous and toxic substances like sodium borohydride and N, N-dimethyl formamide (Khan et al., 2019; Kumar et al., 2015; Pesika et al., 2003; Shirtcliffe et al., 1999; Vickers, 2017; Kumar et al., 2019).

Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) have been produced through various methods, including chemical and physical approaches. However, these methods often require the use of hazardous chemicals and high temperatures (Quaresma et al., 2009). To address this issue, the use of biological processes involving bacteria, enzymes, plants, or plant extracts has been proposed as an environmentally friendly alternative (Schultz et al., 2000; Nair et al., 2002). Biological organisms such as plants, fungi, bacteria, and viruses have the ability to absorb and accumulate metals, acting as reducing agents and controlling the nanostructural properties of metal ions. By employing natural organisms, AgNPs can be biosynthesized in a straightforward, reliable, non-toxic, and eco-friendly manner (Narayanan et al., 2010; Sathishkumar et al., 2010). In comparison to chemical approaches, the process of biological synthesis for producing nanoparticles has a number of benefits, including affordability, accessibility, eco-friendliness, non-toxicity, and the capacity for large-scale manufacturing. Green synthesis uses naturally available reducing agents such as plant extracts, microbes, enzymes, and polysaccharides instead of expensive, environmentally dangerous chemical process. It is easy and practical to use this alternative strategy to deal with hazardous chemical procedures (Du L. et al., 2009).

The Liliaceae plant family includes *Asparagus racemosus* (*A. racemosus*), also known as Satawar, Satamuli, or Satavari. In India, it can be found at lower elevations. In Ayurveda, *A. racemosus* is referred as the “Queen of herbs” due to its connection to fostering love and devotion (Vaidya et al., 2007). As a result of its therapeutic qualities, *A. racemosus* is frequently utilised in Ayurveda. It is used to cure a variety of medical conditions, such as internal heat, chronic fever, seet-veeryam, som rogam, madhur rasam, and madhur vipakam (Frawley, 2000; Vaidya et al., 2007).

The root of *A. racemosus* is acknowledged as an Ayurvedic rasayana, which is thought to provide vigour to the body, promote lifespan, boost immunity, and improve mental performance. Additionally, it is used to treat hepatopathy, tumours, inflammation, neuropathy, dyspepsia, and other illnesses (Frawley, 2000; Vaidya et al., 2007). Furthermore, various therapeutic approaches of *A. racemosus* root extract have been described in numerous pharmacological studies, including antiulcer, antioxidant, antidiarrheal, antidiabetic, and immunomodulatory properties (Sairam et al., 2003). According to descriptions, the root has aphrodisiac, diuretic, rejuvenating, carminative, stomachic, antibacterial, and tonic characteristics in addition to bitter-sweet, emollient, cooling, nervine tonic, constipating, galactogogue, and tonic effects. The treatment of neurological disorders, dyspepsia, diarrhoea, dysentery, tumours, inflammations, hyperdipsia, neuropathy, hepatopathy, cough, bronchitis, hyperacidity, and some infectious diseases is thought to benefit from it (Nighantu et al., 2010; Sairam et al., 2003). Apart from flavonoids, tannins, and phenolic components, the analysis of plant compounds has identified steroidal saponins as the major constituents of *A. racemosus*. The presence of these diverse phytoconstituents opens up possibilities for developing

innovative therapeutic drugs to address a range of diseases (Mishra et al., 2017; Gautam et al., 2009). Due to its numerous medicinal uses and characteristics, *Asparagus racemosus* (*A. racemosus*) is highly revered in Ayurveda. Its root extract has been linked to a number of pharmacological actions and has historically been used to treat a variety of illnesses.

This research focuses on the production of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) using an aqueous extract derived from the rhizome of *A. racemosus*. The synthesized nanoparticles undergo comprehensive characterization through spectrophotometer. Additionally, *in vitro* assays are employed to assess the various therapeutic approaches of synthesized nanoparticles.

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1. Collection of Sample:

Asparagus racemosus rhizomes were purchased from an Ayurvedic shop in Maharashtra, India. For further research, the rhizomes were purchased in powder form.

2.2. Preparation of plant extract:

A quantity of 5 grams of powdered root was combined with 50 mL of distilled water in a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask. The mixture was gently heated for approximately 15-20 minutes and then filtered using a Whatman filter paper. The resulting liquid extract was stored at a temperature of 4°C (Khanal et al., 2022).

A. racemosus rhizomes extract was placed in a 250 ml Erlenmeyer flask and mixed 1 mM aqueous silver nitrate (AgNO₃) solution under constant stirring using a magnetic stirrer at a temperature of 25 ± 2° C. The initially light-yellow solution gradually underwent a color change, transforming into a reddish-brown hue within an hour, indicating the formation of AgNPs. The solution was allowed to incubate, and once the reaction was complete, it was subjected to centrifugation at a speed of 8000 rpm for 40 minutes at a temperature of 20° C. This process was repeated three times for thorough washing. The resulting solution was collected and further centrifuged at 14000 rpm using double-distilled water for 20 minutes (Khanal et al., 2022).

2.3. Phytochemical Screening:

The extracts were qualitatively evaluated for different categories of phytochemicals using established protocols that are widely recognized (Harbone, 1973; Trease and Evans, 1985; Congesta, 2005; Ngameni et al., 2013).

2.3.1. Alkaloid Test: In 1 ml of extract, added a few drops of iodine solution were added and kept at room temperature for few minutes.

The presence of red and brown precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

2.3.2. Tannins Test: In 1ml of the extract, put few drops of 5% FeCl₃ solution was added and the appearance of black, blue, brownish-green colouration showed the presence of tannins.

2.3.3. Flavonoids Test: 1 ml of the extract was mixed with 1 ml of 2% NaOH solution and a few drops of diluted HCL solution was added. If the yellowish colour turns colourless on the addition of dilute HCL indicating the presence of flavonoids.

2.3.4. Saponins Test: 1 ml of the extract was mixed with the same amount of distilled water and kept in water bath for 10 minutes at 50 C. After that added 6 ml of distilled water and leave for 2 minutes. The presence of foam on top indicate saponins are present.

- 2.3.5. Terpenoids Test:** The terpenoid content was determined by mixing 1 mL of the extract and 1 ml of concentrated H₂SO₄. Heat for 2 minutes, greyish colour indicate presence of terpenoids.
- 2.3.6. Steroids Test:** 1 mL of extract and 1 ml chloroform were mixed in test tube. To the reaction mixture 1 ml of concentrated H₂SO₄ was added. No change in colour from violet to bluish green showed the absence of steroids in the extract.
- 2.3.7. Glycosides Test:** The extract, weighing approximately 0.5 gram, was dissolved in 2 ml of glacial acetic acid, which contained 1 drop of 1% FeCl₃ solution. This mixture was then layered with concentrated sulfuric acid. At the interphase, a brown ring was observed, indicating the presence of a deoxy sugar. Below the brown ring, a violet interface ring appeared, located within the acetic acid layer. Additionally, a greenish ring appeared just above the violet ring and gradually spread throughout this layer.
- 2.3.8. Carbohydrate (Reduction of Fehling's):** Each test tube should contain an equal amount of Fehling's solution A and Fehling's solution B, mix thoroughly. Equal amount of extract added. The test tubes can be heated in a water bath, on a Bunsen burner or on a hot plate. Bring the fluid in the test tubes to a mild boil or until it turns brick red in colour. A brick red precipitate of cuprous oxide forms if reducing sugar are present.
- 2.3.9. Anthraquinones Test:** 0.5 mL of the root extract, 0.5mL of dilute hydrochloric acid was added and mixed. Then, few drops of chloroform was added to the mixture and shaken vigorously. The mixture was allowed to settle, and the lower chloroform layer was separated. To the chloroform layer, few drops of dilute ammonia solution was added and observed for the development of a pink or red colour. The appearance of a pink or red colour indicated the presence of anthraquinones in the extract.

2.4. Characterization of Silver Nanoparticles by UV-Vis Spectroscopy:

UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-160) was utilised to characterise the AgNPs and ascertain their biological characteristics. Using UV-vis spectroscopy (Shimadzu UV-160), the absorption spectra of synthesised AgNPs were captured. There were identified peaks that were detected. It assisted in identifying the extract's functional groups and the AgNPs that might be responsible for creating the nanoparticles. By measuring the reaction mixture's wave length in the UV-Vis spectrum with a wavelength resolution of ranging from 200 to 720 nm, the presence of silver nanoparticles was verified.

2.5. Various Therapeutic Approaches of Silver Nanoparticles Synthesized using *Asparagus racemosus*:

2.5.1. Antimicrobial activity:

Prepare a Nutrient Agar Media (NAM) and sterilized the media by autoclaved. Pour the media on sterilized petriplates and after the solidification of media bacteria was spread over the plates by using spreader. With the help of sterile gel puncture, approximately 10 mm diameter of wells was made in the agar plates. Using a micropipette, the drilled wells were poured with 50 µL of the *A. racemosus* AgNP, 50 µL of the *A. racemosus* root extract, and 10 µL of the antibiotic (Ciprofloxain) respectively. Two Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*; one Gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* was being selected for evaluating antimicrobial efficacy of the synthesized AgNP. The zone of inhibition was measured after the plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h (Bindhu et al., 2013).

2.5.2. Antioxidant Activity:

Prepare a stock solution of DPPH by dissolving 0.0072-gram DPPH in 30 ml methanol. Take three test tubes labelled as Blank, Extract and silver particle. Add 1.5 mL of the DPPH stock

solution to each test tube. Then add 50 microlitre of sample in respective tube labelled accordingly. Mix the contents of each test tube thoroughly and let them stand in the dark at room temperature for 30 minutes. Measure the absorbance of each solution using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer at the 517 nm. First take an absorbance of blank sample which contain only 1.5 ml of DPPH stock solution (Ravichandran et al., 2016).

Calculate the percentage of DPPH scavenging activity using the following formula:

$$\text{DPPH scavenging activity (\%)} = \frac{[(\text{Absorbance of control} - \text{Absorbance of sample}) / \text{Absorbance of control}] \times 100}$$

2.5.3. Antimutagenic Activity:

Antimutagens are substances that prevent the formation of mutagenic materials. Their interference can involve various mechanisms such as inhibiting the conversion of promutagenic substances into active mutagens, inactivating mutagens, or preventing mutagenic reactions with DNA. In the Salmonella histidine point mutation assay developed by Ames in 1983, bacteria are spread on agar plates containing a limited amount of histidine in the growth medium. This allows the bacteria to multiply and undergo mutations for a short period. The antimutagenic activity of different plant extracts was evaluated using this assay. Specifically, the effect of *Asparagus racemosus* root extracts on sodium azide-induced mutagenicity were determined. The experimental procedure involved adding 0.5 mL of phosphate buffer to sterilized sealed tubes placed in an ice bath. Subsequently, 0.1 mL of mutagen, 0.1 mL of plant extract, and 0.1 mL of bacterial culture were added and allowed to incubate for 30 minutes. Then, 0.5 mM L-histidine was added and the mixture was immediately poured onto minimal agar plates. After 48 hours of incubation at 37°C, the appearance of revertant colonies was observed (Moldovan et al., 2016).

Silver nanoparticle solution is a dark brown tint, according literature investigations. *A. racemosus* had a light brown hue prior to the addition of AgNO₃, but after being treated with AgNO₃, the colour changed to a dark brown, indicating the synthesis of AgNPs. This colour change is caused by the quantum confinement feature of nanoparticles, which is a size-dependent property that influences the optical quality of the nanoparticles.

3. Result and Discussions:

3.1. Biosynthesis and Characterization of Silver Nanoparticle UV-Vis (Ultraviolet-Visible Spectroscopy):

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Fig 1

Fig 2

Figure 1, 2: *Asparagus racemosus* root extract before and after heating for one hour after adding AgNO₃

UV-vis spectroscopy commonly uses to check the synthesis of freshly produced metal nanoparticles (NPs). It monitors the metals' surface plasmon resonance peaks, which oversee giving them their distinctive visual characteristics. A colour change from light brown to dark brown signifying the creation of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs). The active phytochemicals in the *A. racemosus* root extract are thought to have assisted in the reduction of Ag⁺ ions to Ag⁰, which is responsible for the colour shift. Numerous phytochemicals have been implicated in the past studies as reducing and capping agents for NP production.

Figure 2: UV-Vis Spectroscopy of AgNP

3.2. Phytochemical Screening:

The qualitative phytochemical screening of *Asparagus racemosus* root extract revealed the presence or absence of certain phytochemical constituents. The results of the analysis are as follows:

Sr. No.	Chemical Component	Result
i.	Alkaloid	-
ii.	Tanins	+
iii.	Flavonoids	+
iv.	Saponins	+
v.	Terpenoids	+
vi.	Steroids	+
vii.	Glycosides	+
viii.	Carbohydrate	-
ix.	Anthraquinones	-

Table 1: Phytochemical Screening of *Asparagus racemosus* root extract

3.3. Antimicrobial Activity:

Three different bacteria—*Escherichia coli* (AgNPs), *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*), and *Bacillus subtilis* (*B. subtilis*)—were used to test the antimicrobial activity of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) and root extract produced using *Asparagus racemosus*. The outcomes

were contrasted against the common antibiotic, ciprofloxacin. The zone of inhibition, measured in centimeters, was used as an indicator of antimicrobial activity. The results obtained from the experiment are summarized in Table 2.

When *Asparagus racemosus* AgNPs and root extract were tested for antibacterial activity, it became clear that the AgNPs generally displayed more antimicrobial activity. This shows that the *Asparagus racemosus* derived silver nanoparticles are more effective against the tested bacteria due to their natural antibacterial characteristics. The antimicrobial activity of both the AgNPs and the root extract was generally lower than that of the antibiotic ciprofloxacin, which is a popular and effective antibacterial drug, however this is a crucial distinction to make.

Sample	<i>Escherichia coli</i> (cm)	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (cm)	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> (cm)
A. racemosus AgNP	1.5	2	2
A. racemosus root extract	0.5	1.5	1.2
Standard (Ciprofloxacin)	4	4.5	3.5

3.4. Antioxidant Activity:

The antioxidant activity of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) and root extract synthesised using *Asparagus racemosus* was assessed, by estimating the DPPH scavenging activity. *Asparagus racemosus* had a DPPH scavenging activity of 37.7%, compared to a lower activity of 22.2% in the root extract. When compared to the root extract, the AgNPs had a greater DPPH scavenging activity. These findings imply that the antioxidant activity of the *Asparagus racemosus* AgNPs and root extract is demonstrated by their capacity to scavenge DPPH radicals. The AgNPs, as opposed to the root extract, demonstrated a considerably larger proportion of DPPH scavenging activity, indicating enhanced antioxidant potential.

Sample	Absorbance at 517 nm
A. racemosus AgNP	0.605
racemosus Extract	0.485
Control	0.778

Table 3: Antioxidant Activity

The presence of bioactive substances such flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and other phytochemicals in *Asparagus racemosus* is responsible for the reported antioxidant activity. These substances are said to have strong antioxidant properties that can efficiently combat free radicals and prevent oxidative stress.

3.5. Antimutagenic Activity:

The Ames test was used to assess the antimutagenic properties of root extract and silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) synthesised from *Asparagus racemosus*. The Ames test measures a substance's capacity to cause bacterial mutations in order to determine its mutagenicity. The results of antimutagenic activity of root extract with the help of salmonella histidine point mutation assay of Ames showed that revertant colonies on protocol plates. The control plate contains only distilled water. In order to verify the viability of the bacterial strain employed in

the test, the control plate is utilized as a reference. On the control plate, there are a lot of colonies, which shows that the bacteria are expanding normally.

Figure 3, 4, 5: Antimutagenic Test against AgNP, extract, Control plate

Colonies did not grow when *Asparagus racemosus* AgNPs were present. This indicates that the *Asparagus racemosus*-derived AgNPs had antimutagenic qualities because they stopped the growth of bacteria in the Ames test. This suggests that the AgNPs may be able to prevent bacterial mutations, hence lowering the danger of mutagenesis. Similar to the negative control plate, the plate containing *Asparagus racemosus* root extract had a very small number of colonies. This suggests that the root extract has antimutagenic properties as well, able it to a lesser level than the AgNPs.

The findings imply that root extract and *Asparagus racemosus* AgNPs both have promise as antimutagenic substances. The Ames test revealed antimutagenic activity, which points to their capacity to stop or slow down bacterial mutation. The root extract and AgNPs from *Asparagus racemosus* have antimutagenic properties. These results suggest that *Asparagus racemosus* may be used as a natural source for the production of antimutagenic compounds.

4. Conclusion:

Green nanotechnology is regarded as an environmentally friendly and energy-efficient method for producing nanoparticles without causing harm to the environment. Several plant materials and herbal drugs have been investigated as promising resources for the eco-friendly synthesis of nanoparticles. This research focused on synthesizing silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) using *Asparagus racemosus* root extract and exploring their characterization, phytochemical analysis, and therapeutic potential. The AgNPs were successfully formed and characterized through UV-vis spectroscopy. Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of bioactive compounds like flavonoids and terpenoids, enhancing the AgNPs' therapeutic potential. The AgNPs displayed significant antimicrobial and antioxidant activities, making them promising for combating infections and oxidative stress-related disorders. Overall, this study highlights *Asparagus racemosus*-based AgNPs as versatile therapeutic agents with green synthesis advantages. Further research is needed to explore mechanisms, optimize protocols, and assess in vivo efficacy and safety for nanomedicine applications.

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